

2024

opencitations.net

OpenCitations

Annual Report

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with the advice from the International Advisory Board for OpenCitations

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2024 at a glance

Silvio Peroni

OpenCitations Director

Dear reader, 2024 has been a transitional year at OpenCitations. Daily, we strive to improve our infrastructure and offer better services, in line with our mission and with a strong consideration of the community's requirements and needs. Thus, in the previous months, a significant amount of work took place behind the scenes, particularly with technical and communication aspects. This has been a long journey that began a few years ago, touching several core components of the OpenCitations infrastructure, and which will be evident to the broader audience by 2025. In the meantime, we would like to provide you with a description of all these activities in our brand-new report, which we prepare annually to align the audience with OpenCitations' activities. Enjoy the reading!

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Silvio Peroni". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

205

Unique users
according to the Access Token requests

2 billion

Unique citations

> 15 M

Data requests
via API calls

OpenCitations' 5 areas of action

OpenCitations' mission is to harvest and openly publish accurate and comprehensive metadata describing the world's academic publications and the scholarly citations that link them, and to preserve persistent access to this information by secure archiving.

To overcome the limitations and achieve its overall objectives, OpenCitations identified five activities to focus on, and is still pursuing the following areas of action* in planning its activities yearly:

- **Collect open references from scholarly sources**
- **Expand the number of open citations across the entire scholarly domain**
- **Expand the team**
- **Governance evolution**
- **Community building**

Mission

<https://zenodo.org/record/6976670>

Uniqueness

<https://zenodo.org/record/6976696>

Plans

<https://zenodo.org/record/6976691>

Area of Action 1

Collecting open references from scholarly sources

Activity 1

During 2024, OpenCitations has ingested citation data from a variety of data sources, using [a new ingestion workflow](#) launched at the end of 2023, which has made it possible to facilitate the metadata crosswalk processes between the new sources' data models and the OpenCitations Data Model, thus making it easier to incorporate new data sources.

The sources currently managed by OpenCitations are:

Crossref
DOI
(2018)

DataCite
DOI
(2022)

NIH-OCC
PMID
(2022)

OpenAIRE
DOI, PMID,
PMC, ARXIV
(2023)

JALC
DOI
(2023)

Area of Action 2

Expand the number of open citations across the entire scholarly domain

Unique Citations in
OpenCitations Index
(as for December 2024)

2 billion

Throughout 2024, the OpenCitations team has worked on :

- strengthening the technical infrastructure by addressing issues within OpenCitations Meta, to guarantee regular releases of the OpenCitations Index throughout 2025;
- releasing the June 2024 **dump of OpenCitations Meta**, of the bibliographic metadata from all the publications involved in the OpenCitations Meta;
- releasing the July 2024 **dump of OpenCitations Index**, containing more than 2 billion citations;
- developing **HERITRACE**, a new tool designed to streamline data curation. This semantic data management system is tailored specifically for the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) sector. HERITRACE is an editor for curating bibliographic data, allowing users to track provenance and monitor changes over time.

→ Massari, A., & Peroni, S. (2024). HERITRACE: Tracing evolution and bridging data for streamlined curatorial work in the GLAM domain. arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.00477.

Area of Action 3

Expand the team

During 2025, OpenCitations development team welcomed 3 new developers and a Chief Technology Officer, for a total of 11 people now working daily on OpenCitations, including Research Fellows and PhD students:

Ivan Heibi

Chief Technology Officer (CTO)

- Supervision and management of the technical infrastructure of OpenCitations
- Supervision and management of the development team

Marta Soricetti

Software Developer

- Development of a tool designed to automatically annotate in-text citations in academic PDFs as part of the GraspOS Project.

Lorenzo Paolini

Software Developer

- Development of Large Language Models (LLMs) for classification and generation tasks to extract and understand the semantics behind the act of referencing in research works

Mario Petrella

Systems Administrator

- Management, maintenance and implementation of the server and components of OpenCitations' technical infrastructure

Area of Action 4

Governance evolution

During 2024, we worked to develop the open governance structure of OpenCitations further. For administrative convenience, OpenCitations is managed by the **Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata at the University of Bologna**. Currently, the organizational bodies included in the OpenCitations governance are: the Directors, the International Advisory Board, and the Council, regulated and described in the documents "[Organizational Bodies and Finances](#)", and "[Rules for Membership](#)".

Governance Evolution Working Group

The OpenCitations "Governance Evolution" working group, which started in 2022, ended its activities in 2023. The activity of the group resulted in the drafting of a governance reform document in cooperation with the legal department of the University of Bologna. In 2024, a discussion was opened with a professor at the same university specialising in administrative law who reviewed the draft reform and proposed various reform scenarios compatible with the legal status of OpenCitations. 2026 is the expected year to finalise the governance evolution according to the resolutions of the working group.

Renewal of the International Advisory Board

After the pilot four-year mandate of the International Advisory Board of OpenCitations (the strategic body of OpenCitations → [Organizational Bodies and Finances](#)), during 2024 the Governance Evolution working group raised the need to renew the International Advisory Board composition, with subsequent renewal processes taking place every three years. The elections of the members of the new International Board on OpenCitations were held in the first week of December. The voting council selected eight members among ten candidates who are strongly committed to open scholarship.

The new members of the International Board for OpenCitations are:

- **Marcel R. Ackermann (Team Lead of dblp Computer Science Bibliography)**
- **Maria Gould (Product Director at DataCite and Director of ROR)**
- **Catriona MacCallum (Director of Open Science, Hindawi Open Access Publisher)**
- **Philippe Mongeon (Associate Professor and Chair of the Department of Information Science at University of Montreal)**
- **Cameron Neylon (Professor of Research Communications, Centre for Culture and Technology, Curtin University)**
- **Iratxe Puebla (Director of Make Data Count)**
- **Dominika Tkaczyk (Director of Data Science at CrossRef)**
- **Didier Torny (on behalf of the French Open Science Committee)**
- **Ludo Waltman (Professor of Quantitative Science Studies and Deputy Director, Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University)**

During 2024, OpenCitations held three International Advisory Board Meetings and an annual Council Meeting.

Area of Action 5 Community Building

Being a community-based infrastructure organization, OpenCitations has community outreach as one of its areas of focus. To identify and reach out to wider communities and new stakeholders, in July 2022, OpenCitations started a Community Building Working Group, whose activities kept on throughout 2023 and 2024. We enhanced the communication of OpenCitations' news using OpenCitations Blog, social media and communications partnerships.

The communications team has been collaborating with the Communications Office and the Graphic Office of the University of Bologna to prepare a rebranding campaign launched in 2025.

Community Building Working Group

The OpenCitations "Community Building" working group, which started its activities in 2022, met three times during 2024, with the participation of the Communications Director Chiara Di Giambattista, and members from the International Advisory Board. After a first phase, in 2023, dedicated to the identification of the stakeholders of OpenCitations and to guide the launch and promotion of the technical workflow revision, in 2024 the working group focused on the outreach tools and strategies, by providing valuable feedback on the OpenCitations Blog editorial plan, providing guidance on the OpenCitations rebranding campaign (to be announced in 2025), and suggesting tools to foster interaction and participation during OpenCitations events.

We enhanced the communication of OpenCitations' news using OpenCitations Blog, social media and communications partnerships.

Social Media Management

Social media platforms (X; Mastodon; LinkedIn; Threads) were used to share and promote the blog content, the participation in events and major technical developments.

We created an OpenCitations profile on [Bluesky](#).

OpenCitations Blog

The OpenCitations blog is currently hosted on the academic blogs platform Hypotheses.org (<https://opencitations.hypotheses.org/>), and the blog feed is featured on Rogue Scholar, an archive of science blogs aiming to index full-text of blog posts, establish a full-text search, and register DOIs and metadata for all posts.

During 2024, we started the blog series "Who's using OC?", to showcase our community and promote the projects that are currently using OpenCitations data to develop tools and services. We published a first blog post dedicated to [dblp](#):

- **Chiara Di Giambattista (September 25, 2024). #1 Who's using OC? The dblp computer science bibliography. OpenCitations blog. Retrieved April 27, 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/12cme>**

In 2024, we published seven blog posts on the OpenCitations Blog. Compared to 2023, the blog experienced a growth in website traffic, as shown in the graph below (information for 2025 is incomplete):

The most viewed blog post this year was the following:

- **Chiara Di Giambattista (June 10, 2024). Remembering David M. Shotton, Founder and Co-Director of OpenCitations. OpenCitations blog. Retrieved June 20, 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/11seo>**

Participation in events and conferences

During 2024, OpenCitations participated in numerous events and conferences that helped reach out to a wider community.

17 January 2024

La valutazione della ricerca alla prova dei fatti (Florence, Italy)

Invited talk of Silvio Peroni in the context of the event "La valutazione della ricerca alla prova dei fatti" organized from Wikimedia Italia and University of Florence.

Peroni, S. (2024, January 17). Dati bibliografici e citazionali aperti per la trasparenza della valutazione della ricerca: il caso di OpenCitations. La valutazione della ricerca alla prova dei fatti, Florence, Italy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10636030>

8 February 2024

Open Science Cafè (online)

Invited talk of Silvio Peroni presenting OpenCitations in the context of the online talk series Open Science Cafè.

Peroni, S. (2024, February 8). OpenCitations. Open Science Cafè, Virtual. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10635993>

23 February 2024

CEUR Workshop (Brixen, Italy)

Talk by Elia Rizzetto entitled " Mapping bibliographic metadata collections: the case of OpenCitations Meta and OpenAlex".

Rizzetto, E.; Peroni, S., Mapping bibliographic metadata collections: the case of OpenCitations Meta and OpenAlex, in: CEUR Workshop Proceedings, CEUR-WS, «CEUR WORKSHOP PROCEEDINGS», 2024, 3643, pp. 155 – 168 (Proceedings of the 20th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science, IRCDL 2024, Bressanone – Brixen, Italia, 2024)

29 February 2024

LERU Information & Open Access Policy Group meeting (Milan, Italy)

Presentation by Silvio Peroni on open peer reviews and open citation indexes done during the internal Information & Open Access Policy Group meeting of the League of European Research Universities (LERU).

Peroni, S. (2024, February 29). Examples of decoupling different functions of publishers: peer-reviewing processes and open citation indexes. LERU Information & Open Access Policy Group meeting, Milan, Italy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728030>

23 July 2024

GraspOS 3rd Training Event (online)

Presentation by Silvio Peroni given in the context of the 3rd Training event of GraspOS entitled "Citation and their meaning - or why we cite".

Peroni, S. (2024, July 23). Citations and their meaning – or why we cite. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12800675>

21-23 October 2024

EOSC Symposium (Berlin)

Poster presentation by Silvio Peroni and Chiara Di Giambattista, selected in the context of the EOSC Symposium and entitled "OpenCitations: redesigning an open infrastructure according to the FAIR principles".

Peroni, S., & Di Giambattista, C. (2024). OpenCitations: redesigning an open infrastructure according to the FAIR principles. EOSC Symposium 2024, Berlin, Germany. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14871494>

5 November 2024

SILICE: La creación de un marco abierto para la información científica

Presentation from the online talk "An overview of OpenCitations, an open infrastructure to transform research assessment practices" given by Chiara Di Giambattista during the seminar "SILICE: La creación de un marco abierto para la información científica".

Di Giambattista, C. (2024, November 8). An overview of OpenCitations, an open infrastructure to transform research assessment practices. "SILICE: La creación de un marco abierto para la información científica", Madrid. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056726>

Events hosted by OpenCitations

OpenCitations Annual Webinar and Council Meeting

On December 10, OpenCitations held the OpenCitations Annual Webinar for the OpenCitations Council members, an internal event during which the OpenCitations director provided an overview of OpenCitations and presented the latest updates and future developments.

Project partnerships, funded applications and R&D projects

European Research Council (2023-2024)

In 2023, OpenCitations received a grant (Service Contract ERCEA/2023/MLVP/0007) from the European Research Council, to appoint personnel to work on the mapping of OpenCitations identifiers to OpenAlex identifiers in the context of the project “PIDs for containers”. The full analysis is presented in the following article involving OpenCitations Developer Elia Rizzetto:

Rizzetto, E.; Peroni, S., Mapping bibliographic metadata collections: the case of OpenCitations Meta and OpenAlex, in: CEUR Workshop Proceedings, CEUR-WS, «CEUR WORKSHOP PROCEEDINGS», 2024, 3643, pp. 155 – 168 (Proceedings of the 20th Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science, IRCDL 2024, Bressanone – Brixen, Italia, 2024)

GraspOS (2023-ongoing)

[GraspOS project](#) started on January 1, 2023 to create an open and trusted federated infrastructure for next-generation research metrics and indicators. GraspOS aims to build and operate a data infrastructure to support the policy reforms and pave the way towards a responsible research assessment system that embeds OS practices and accelerates its adoption in Europe. In GraspOS, OpenCitations is involved as one of the Data Asset Sources, which provides both the raw and the structured data that can be used to directly support OS-aware RRA processes or to calculate indicators or collect evidence that can be of value in these processes. The researchers from OpenCitations and the University of Bologna are contributing to GraspOS by developing a tool for the extraction of citation data from PDFs, enriched with additional information on the reasons for citing (because the citing entity reuses a method described in the cited entity, for agreeing with the claims of the cited entity, etc.) through the implementation of machine-learning systems. During 2024, OpenCitations was involved in the work packages of the project, also collaborating with colleagues from [OpenAIRE](#).

SCOSS Family

After participating in the second funding cycle of the SCOSS program (2019-2023), OpenCitations is now part of the [SCOSS Family](#), the community of practice gathering the Infrastructures across all of SCOSS' pledging rounds. This involves participation in the internal working groups that share resources and explore ways of collaboration, and of creating impact and a stronger open ecosystem.

Invest in Open Infrastructure

In April, OpenCitations was listed in [Infra Finder](#), a tool developed by Invest in Open Infrastructure to foster discovery, adoption, and investment in open infrastructure services. The intuitive interface and usability make Infra Finder a helpful tool that could make OpenCitations and other infrastructure services more visible to a wider and diverse community.

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

OpenCitations is one of the supporters of the [Barcelona Declaration](#), a key initiative launched in April 2024 aimed at fostering open access to scholarly information and advancing the principles of open science. This aligns perfectly with OpenCitations' mission to promote transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in scholarly communication. By supporting the Barcelona Declaration, OpenCitations reaffirms its commitment to the shared values of openness, inclusivity, and the democratisation of knowledge, all of which are integral to creating a more equitable and accessible academic landscape for researchers, institutions, and the global community.

Other Catalogues and Collections

OpenCitations is currently included in the [OpenAIRE Service Catalogue](#), in the former [EOSC Marketplace \(now EOSC EU Node\)](#) and in the [JISC Collections](#).

Financial report

Expenditure for the year 2024:

Salaries for three computer specialists, one Policy Advocate and Community Outreach Officer, and the OpenCitations Manager / Accountant / Administrator	112.509,42 €
Costs of conference attendance	762,13 €
Crossref subscriptions	542,52 €
Hardware	119,34 €
Web services and tools	469,37 €
Total	114.402,78 €

Income for the year 2024:

Funder Name	Country
Berner Fachhochschule	Switzerland
CERN	Switzerland
Dalhousie University	Canada
École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich	Switzerland
European University Institute	Italy
French Open Science Committee	France
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Belgium
Kwantlen Polytechnic University	Canada
McMaster University	Canada
Nipissing University	Canada
Royal Danish Library	Denmark
Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Tampere University including Tampere University Hospital	Finland
Technische Universiteit Delft Library	The Netherlands

Income for the year 2024:

Funder Name	Country
Universität Bern	Switzerland
Universität St Gallen	Switzerland
Universität Zürich	Switzerland
Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt	Germany
Université de Fribourg	Switzerland
Université de Montréal	Canada
Université de Neuchâtel	Switzerland
Université Libre de Bruxelles	Belgium
University of Alberta	Canada
University of Durham	United Kingdom
University of Newcastle	Australia
University of Nottingham	United Kingdom
University of Ottawa	Canada
University of Saskatchewan	Canada
University of Sussex	United Kingdom
University of Toronto	Canada
Total revenues for 2024	191.251,68€

Contacts

OpenCitations

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Social Media

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/opencitations.bsky.social>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/opencitations/>

Mastodon: <https://scicomm.xyz/@opencitations>

Threads: <https://www.threads.net/@opencitations>

X: <http://www.twitter.com/opencitations>

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